

Polymer nanocomposite materials for thermoelectric applications

I.Vijitha^{a,b}, C. Vijayakumar Nair^{a,b}, Biswapriya Deb^{a,b,*}

^aCSIR- National Institute for Interdisciplinary Science and Technology, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India

^bAcSIR- Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research, India

*Email: biswapriya.deb@niist.res.in

Thermoelectricity is the direct conversion of temperature differences to electric voltage and vice versa(1). A good thermoelectric material should have high electrical conductivity to minimize Joule heating, low thermal conductivity to prevent thermal shorting, and a high Seebeck coefficient for maximum conversion of heat to electrical power or electrical power to cooling. Besides being easily processable and scalable compared to the inorganic counterparts, the most conducting polymer has the inherent advantage of having very low thermal conductivity(2). Despite considerable scientific know-how generated in the last decade, the practical implementation of the polymer nanocomposite based devices needed to address important factors like adopting a materials/device fabrication scheme with better batch reproducibility, innovation in device design to maximize power conversion and finding the right interconnects for low-loss transport. Herein, we prepared several polymer-nanocomposite systems and explored their strengths and limitations for practical applications. The polymer components consisted of fused thiophenes, PEDOT and PANI, etc. while single/multi-walled carbon nanotubes and several important inorganic nanostructures (metal QDs, metal oxides, Bi₂Te₃, etc.) were used to form the desired composites. For each combination, the percolation threshold for conductivity obtained by varying polymer/nanocomposite weight ratio. Our experiments showed that apart from achieving the right balance of electrical/thermal conductivity and thermo e.m.f., the total device resistance played a crucial role in extracting optimized power output.

polymer, hybrid, nanocomposite, thermoelectrics

References

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